

An experimental work on tactile interaction: how to give to the user the possibility to adopt an engaged or a receptive attitude?

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Research Paper

Abstract

The sense of touch, which is very emotional and could give the impression to be in 'contact' with others, is not so often used in communication devices. Thus, our goal is to develop a tactile mobile phone, providing an emotionally rich experience to the user. From earlier experimentations conducted with users manipulating mock-ups, we enhanced two main kinds of communicating attitudes. People were either "engaged", since they act toward the others to contact them, or they were "receptive", trying to attract others toward themselves. We used the potential of numeric technologies to develop two tactile avatars corresponding to the "engaged" and the "receptive" attitudes. An experimental study showed the influence of using one or the other avatar in specific situations.

Key words: Tactile, Communication, Interaction, Intentions, Perception

1 The advantages of the tactile sense in mobile phone conversations

Over the last ten years mobile phones became one of the most popular communication tools. By enabling us to speak and to listen, to read and to write and even to show and to see almost instantaneously over large distances, they extended our action possibilities. In the great majority of cases, especially for non-professional usages, mobile phone is linked to what Jakobson calls the “phatic” function of communication: when the relational aspects are more important than the informational content of the messages (Jakobson, 1963). Plenty of examples can be found in our social life: discussing with shopkeepers, sending our best wishes each new year, etc. The need of such kinds of exchanges made the mobile phone sales explode in 1997. Virtual greeting cards exchanged between relatives? Or phone calls between lovers are relevant examples where the informational value of the message is very near to zero, but the contacts allow to attest that we are here for the others, that we are present. Voice intonation is one of the markers of the phatic function. But there are also other important phatic signals necessary for the mutual recognition and attesting mutual interest: shaking hands, smiling (or other appropriated facial expressions) doing expressive gestures, etc. Those phatic gestures have two main goals: firstly, they are necessary to initiate the conversation (by showing that people are disposable to speak and to listen to each other) and secondly, they enhance the main message delivered by the voice channel. Indeed, Birdwhistell (1970), who studied behaviors in communication, showed that forms of communicational behavior perceived with the eyes are very similar to those perceived with the ears (Birdwhistell, 1970). To convey those phatic signs, mobile phone can be frustrating. First, it is impossible to have any idea about the communicational stance of a contact before starting the conversation. Secondly, audio communication has only a temporal dimension: as soon as my friend stops speaking, he disappears, I can not attest he is still on line. Video communication could be a solution. However, due to the limited size of the screen (on a mobile phone) or to the fact that the screen is split in various windows that could be superposed (in the case of computer applications). Thus, what a partner sees is very uncertain.

The use of tactile modality in distal communication could be of a great interest in all those situations: touching friends to feel their presence, caressing to signify emotions or intentions, grasping or tapping to give more weight to what I say or to give my agreement to what others

are saying. In this context our aim is to design communicating products using tactile stimulation to convey emotions.

2 Related work

Numerous tactile communication tools have already been developed and evaluated, such as the ComTouch of the MIT Media Lab (Chang, O'modhrain, Jacob., Gunther & Ishii, 2002). On the other hand, a lot of technologies for tactile stimulation are developed: pins matrices using piezo-electric or electro magnetic actuators (Benali-Khoudja, 2004), electric discharges to directly stimulate the nerves terminations (Bach-Y-Rita, 2003) and even electro active polymers (Konyo & Tadokoro, 2004). But the spatial resolution of these devices remains lower than the resolution perceived by our fingers: 2 or 3 mm between each dot when our fingers can detect two stimulations distant of about 1 mm. Thus, they don't allow to simulate accurate virtual textures. Bach-y-Rita (Bach-y-Rita, 2003) set up experiments proving that complex images and forms (such as faces) could be perceived using tactile stimulations via an active exploration of the virtual space: the user needs to explore the surrounding space to recognize shapes. It is the link between a displacement of a receptive field and a modification of the tactile sensation that provides the perception of an object. Furthermore, in a previous research (Lenay, Gapenne, Hanneton, Marque & Genouel, 2003) revealed the mutual perception of two persons sharing a same virtual space. The poverty of the sensory input, compensated by the richness of action possibilities is precisely the property we want to exploit to develop a product engaging the user in a pleasurable and emotionally rich experience.

3 Challenges of the project

Like the majority of other digital products, the mobile phone already offers a very wide range of functionalities (as well as each functionality of the mobile phone can be found in a huge amount of other products). However, it provides very poor interaction possibilities, using very cognitive interfaces, often limited to buttons and screens, with a complete disconnection between the functional component and the function itself (Wensveen, Djajadiningrat, Overbeeke, 2004). That makes it very difficult for the user to have a mental representation of

how these products work. Developing tangible interfaces using physical moving parts and involving a wide range of user's perceptual motor skills is a first step to make the object transparent and easily acceptable (Guénand, 2006). However, as Caroline Hummels (Hummels, 2005) underlines it with her concept of 'resonance', it also relies on the ability to take into account our cognitive and emotional skills. To resonate, and to remain pleasurable to use over a long time period after purchasing, the product has to meet the standards of performance and behavior it evokes. In this context, both the interaction with the mobile phone and the interaction possibilities between communicating users have to be designed. Thus, the success of the tactile mobile phone, in terms of acceptability, will rely on a perfect coherence between the design of the interaction with the interface and the design of the interpersonal interaction.

4 Mock-up manipulation: observations of users communicational stances

In a previous work done on a tactile mobile phone offering rich interaction possibilities by the usage of a tangible interface, we mobilized participative design methodologies. Participants had to manipulate junk materials and everyday life objects pretending they were mobile phones. This “interaction relabeling” (Hummels, Djajadiningrat & Overbeeke, 2001) promotes fun and playful attitudes, and creates a context that allow creativity potentials to emerge (Frishberg, 2006). The observed relevant and meaningful gestures of interaction were then integrated into articulated prototypes made of foam and cardboard. Subjects had then to simulate the usage of the device by “playing” a complete scenario (i.e. to call a friend, answer to a call, dial a message, take a picture, send the message and activate tactile mode). On these rough mock-ups interfaces were made tangible: each favorite contact is embodied in a physical part on the mobile phone. Through the observation of the use of the models and the verbalizations of the testers, we enlightened different attitudes regarding the way one person contacts another.

- Either the user moves the tangible parts embodying the persons he wants to communicate with toward him: «I do not move myself but I change the location of my friend to make the contact with me » This is the “receptive” attitude.
- Or the user moves something embodying himself toward the others: «I engage myself and move toward my friend ». This is the “engaged” attitude.

From these two observed communicational stances, we have built two models as being two tangible metaphors, transforming cognitive operating and materializing both the “receptive” attitude and “engaged“ attitude of people getting in contact with others. Thus, we enhance the designer’s responsibility toward user communicational attitudes, since the moving parts of the product and their arrangement can induce very different behaviors that can be compatible or in opposition with user’s emotions. To develop a transparent, resonating and fully acceptable product, it is also a responsibility of the designer to allow the interpersonal tactile interaction to be coherent with these observed communicational stances. The benefit is that the physical product would make the user feel the new interaction possibilities it offers. In this context, our question is: *How could the tactile interaction space offer the possibility for the user to adopt an engaged or a more receptive communicational attitude and to let him perceive the attitudes of his contacts?*

5 Experimental work on tactile interaction in a shared virtual space

5.1 Description of the experimental apparatus

As the tactile interaction could not be implemented on our foam prototypes we used the following experimental set-up (Figure 1).

Figure 1: experimental set-up and participants in usage situation

The system is made of 2 web linked computers. On each computer is plugged a graphic tablet (associated with a stylus) and a dynamic tactile stimulator made of two Braille cells (what makes a 4x4 pins matrix). The software “TACTOS”, developed at the Compiègne University of Technology, carries out a coupling between the position of the stylus on the tablet and the position of a receptive field and an image body on the screen. The receptive field is a matrix of 4x4 receptive elements. When a receptive element of a subject meets the image body of his/her partner, the corresponding pin on the stimulating matrix is activated.

This experimental device allows tactile encounters between blind people or blindfolded participants. It also meets the design expectations of the tangible mobile phones described in the previous part of the paper, since the user can displace a tangible object (the stylus) in a 2D virtual shared space.

5.2 “Engaged” and “receptive” virtual bodies

In the real everyday life, there is a coincidence between the touching subject and the touched subject: I can not touch someone or something without being touched myself. However, when a technical mediation is used for distal touch, the perceiving body (what is used to touch the environment) can be separated from the image body (what is given to be touched by others): touching without being touched and being touched without touching become possible situations. Thus, our assumption is that we can take advantage of different perceiving and images bodies to express “engaged” and “receptive” communicational stances. As we observed it during the tangible mock-ups manipulations, the “engaged” attitude corresponds to situations where the user wants to rich a contact and displace an element of the interface embodying himself/herself towards elements embodying his/her contacts. The research of the contact is then very active. The avatar or the body of the subject in the interaction space has to facilitate this active research, by enabling the perception of a large area (like having large goggles): this would increase the probability to meet someone else. For this “engaged” attitude, being perceived is not the most important, so we chose a small image body. On the other hand, a “receptive” communicational stance corresponds to a more passive behavior: the subject doesn't move, but makes the contacts come to him/her (like having a pink shirt to be highly visible). In this situation, attracting others is the main point: perceiving a large area becomes less important than being perceived by others over a large area. That is why a small perceiving body has been chosen. Thus, two kinds of bodies (illustrated in the Figure 2) were designed and experimentally tested.

Figure 2 : tested virtual tactile bodies A (engaged) and B (receptive) and their equivalent in the vision world

The body A is composed of a 8x8 pixels image body and a 32x32 pixels receptive body and corresponds to the body that would meet the needs of someone having an “engaged” communicational attitude. The body B has a 32x32 pixels image body and a 8x38 pixels receptive body. This one would better fit with the attitude of someone adopting a receptive attitude. The virtual shared space is a 800x600 pixels window.

The figure below (Figure 3) illustrates what subjects perceives when they come in contact to each other in the virtual shared space. Examples of situations with both subjects with A bodies , both subject with B bodies and with an A-B body combination are presented. The pins on the stimulator matrix are represented with white dots when they are inactive (low position: the subject is not stimulated) and with colored dots when they are activated (high position: the subject feels a stimulation).

	Positions of the subjects 1 and 2	Stimulations on the braille cell of the subject 1	Stimulations on the braille cell of the subject 2
Both subject with A bodies			
Both subject with B bodies			
One subject with an A body and one subject with a B body			

Figure 3 : perceptive crossing between two A-type bodies

We can notice that there is no difference in perception when users have both A or both B bodies : in both cases, if one of the subject is stimulated his/her partner is also stimulated and the stimulations are symmetrical. Thus, in the next experiments we only tested A-A and A-B combinations. However, if the two subjects have not the same bodies, there is no symmetry anymore. Indeed, the subject who has the A body (subject 1 in the previous table) is much more stimulated than his/her partner who has a B body (subject 2 in the previous table). In extreme cases, someone with an A body can touch someone with a B body without being touched!

Our assumption is that there could be an interest for the user to have antisymmetric virtual bodies. Indeed it is very intuitive that an engaged person, with a large perceiving body, will easily find a receptive person, whose image body is large. In other words, A body type should be more convenient to find things, while B body type should be more efficient to be found. Thus, we imagined a guiding task for the tactile interaction experiment that could verify our assumptions:

The A body, with its larger perceptive field should be suitable to follow the other. But the A body also has a small image body. Thus, the guide will have to be careful not to lose him. On the other hand, the B body, with its large image body will be easy to follow. Furthermore, as its perceptive field is small, it ensures that the user can not perceive without being perceived himself. Thus, participants who will have a B body should guide their partner very carefully. These experiments are described in the next part of the paper.

5.3 Participants

Eight persons took part to the experiment. Among them, only two already had an experience of the TACTOS system, since they had already used it during shape exploration experiments, but never in mutual perception experiments. During the tasks, participants were blindfolded to limit their sensory input to tactile and proprioceptive modalities. They also were placed in separated rooms and could communicate to each other in any other manner than the TACTOS system.

5.4 Experimental procedure

Before starting experiments, the way the system works was explained to testers, and they could freely experiment it during few minutes to get familiar with the tablet and with the kind of perception they had when they “meet” their partner in the interaction space.

Then subjects were asked to follow a path: one of the subjects is being told the path, and has to guide his partner along the way. This last one has to be cooperative and to try to “keep in touch” with the guide. As the subject who is the guide was blindfolded to keep consistent experimental conditions, dots were placed (equally spaced) on the tablet and the way was

vocally told to him: a direction was indicated each time a dot was reached by the following participant. Their goal was to try get the higher score possible : to reach *together* a maximum number of dots. They had 3 min per path.

The three configurations of virtual bodies (a A guiding a A, a A guiding a B and a B guiding a A) were tested and for each couple of participants, each subject (1 and 2 in the next table) was alternatively guiding and guided. The 6 paths used for these 6 conditions are described in the next table (table 1):

Guide / Body	1 / A	2 / A	1 / A	2 / A	1 / B	2 / B
Guided / Body	2 / A	1 / A	2 / B	1 / B	2 / A	1 / A
Path	1	2	3	4	5	6

Table 1 : paths used for the guiding task

5.5 Result of the experiment : higher scores when participants have different virtual bodies

The next figures (Figure 4) illustrate typical recorded trajectories of the guide and of the guided person on the path 4 (cf Table 1). The X-axis and the Y-axis are graduated in pixels : 800x600 pixels are the total dimensions of the interaction space. The starting point and the dots that the participants have to reach have also been represented on the trajectories.

When both subjects have A bodies, there is a coincidence and a reciprocity in their perception: as soon as one perceives the other, he is also perceived. The guiding person goes along the path with a regular motion. After having done some circular movements to detect the direction in which the guide goes, the guided person starts to oscillate around the (moving) position of his partner. Thus, both get regular tactile stimulations: the guide perceives that the other is following, and the guided subject can do a better anticipation of the trajectory than if he/she would have tried to keep a constant contact. Then, the guide is asked to change direction. As the guided subject was still oscillating in the first direction, the regular pulsating contact between subjects does not occur any more. The guide comes back were he/she perceives his/her partner the last time, while the guided who feels lost, starts to make larger movements around the position of his/her last stimulation until he/she finds the guide again. This process is then repeated at each change in direction.

Figure 4 : Example of trajectories of the subjects on the path 4, with both A bodies

Figure 5 : Example of trajectories on the path 4, when the guide has a B body and the guided subject has an A body

Figure 6 : Example of trajectories on the path 4 when the guide has an A body and the guided subject has a B body

If the guide has a B body, as the image body is large, he will easily be perceived by his partner. This will be accentuated by the fact that the partner has a A body type, which enables to perceive over a large area. Furthermore, in this configuration the guide has a small perceiving body, and the guided person a small image body. Thus, to feel that his partner is following, the guide will have to move very carefully. Thus, in the Figure 5, we can notice that the guide does not go forward with a straight trajectory but proceeds by steps: he

regularly comes back to feel the partner following him. The following participant can perceive the guide from a larger distance than in the previous case. Thus he can keep in touch with fewer oscillations and progress more rapidly. At the opposite, we could immediately guess that if the guide has a A body and the guided a B body (Figure 6), the situation becomes dramatic: it will be very difficult for the guided to perceive his partner while the guide (who will be easily stimulated) will think that his partner is following. The following subject always feels lost and the progression of the couple is very difficult and slow.

To evaluate how the couples of participants succeeded in the task, we measured the length of the path done by the guided one. For this we simply counted the number of dots reached. The scores are gathered in the next table (table 2). As each member of each couple was alternatively guiding his/her partner and guided by his/her partner, there are two scores per couple and per configuration (for example, the couple 2 in the “A guiding A” configuration first scored 3, then they exchanged their roles and scored 1).

	Performances of participants (number of dots reached)		
	A guiding A	B guiding A	A guiding B
Couple 1	2	5	5
	2	5	3
Couple 2	3	1	1
	1	0	1
Couple 3	2	3	1
	2	2	1
Couple 4	5	3	0
	5	3	3
Total	22	25	16

Table 2 : performances of the couples of subjects for the guiding task

The preliminary results we get from this experiment confirm the expected hypothesis for the optimal combination, since the highest scores have been obtained when the guide used a B body and his/her partner a A body. Having a large image body and a reduced perceiving field (body B) is efficient for the guiding task, while having a large perceiving field and a small image body (body A) is better for following tasks. An other comment we can make is about the role of the antisymmetry of the virtual bodies: two different bodies enable better results than two identical ones.

Thus, in communication situations we can imagine to let to the user the possibility to adapt his body not only according to his own goals and intentions, but also by taking into account the intentions and the emotions of his partner.

6 Conclusions and discussion : how to exploit these results to design emotive user interfaces?

This paper presents a work done on the design of a communication device involving the tactile modality. Tactile stimulations produced by Braille cells are used to share emotions by engaging users in a rich interaction experience where they can express intentions and perceive the intentionality of their contacts. The observations on users manipulating articulated mock-ups and playing communication scenarios underlined a latent need of users: they express different attitudes, “engaged” or “receptive” in communicational situations, or more generally in every condition of interaction (when they want to initiate the communication for example). These observations also showed that this stance is dynamically expressed through movements on tangible interfaces. Thus, the tactile interaction has to be coherent with these observations to perfectly match the interaction with the product and the interaction between users. The work done on the tactile interaction design shows that it is possible to use the potential of digital technologies to develop avatars that are advantageous for each one of the “engaged” and the “receptive” attitudes. This can be done by decoupling the image body (what I let the other see from me) and the perceiving body (what allows me to perceive my environment). The experiments we set up provide preliminary elements for the interaction space design. It shows that having a large image body and a reduced perceiving field is efficient for tasks where users need to be “seen”, for example to guide others, to attract them or to show things: that is the “receptive” attitude. On the contrary, having a large perceiving field and a small image body fits better with an “engaged” attitude. It is more efficient to find things in the environment and to follow others. Thus, we should offer the possibility to the user to dynamically choose his/her virtual body according to the situation.

We can also mention the interest of the very minimalist experimental conditions we used for the tactile perception study. Indeed, thanks to the simplicity of the system, the results can have a much more general value on our perception of others as intentional beings and also on how we can mutually express and understand intentions and emotions. Of course, before

being integrated in a “final” tactile interaction device or to a tactile mobile phone, the design of this interaction has to be refined, and experiments have to be repeated on a larger number of users. However, this preliminary work could be a starting point to determine the factors that would influence or that would reflect the attitudes of the users in interpersonal interaction situations. Thus, the following steps of this development will be to find some applications (such as games or instant messengers) that let a large place to communication and that elicit a wide range of emotions.

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